

300-700 nm were recorded with spectrophotometer VSU-2P.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses (Table 1) show the formation of complexes of stoichiometries; 1:1, 1:2, 2:3 and 1:3 (metal:ligand). The colours of complexes range from white to yellow to red. The melting points of complexes fall in the range of melting points of their respective ligands except those of HDPO. The molar conductance values of chloride complexes of MDPO, BDPO and HDPO indicate them to be essentially non-electrolytes (Δ 10.92, 15.95 and 15.32 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$, respectively). Similarly, the perchlorate complexes are formulated as, $[\text{Fe}(\text{MDPO})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_3$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{EDPO})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{BDPO})(\text{ClO}_4)_2(\text{ac})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ (Δ 67.36, 56.36, 32.80 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$, respectively). The nitrate complex of MDPO is a 2:3 electrolyte and that of EDPO is a 1:1 electrolyte (Δ 48.01 and 20.40 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$, respectively) which are formulated as $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{MDPO})_3(\text{NO}_3)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{EDPO})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2](\text{NO}_3)$. However, the corresponding BDPO complex is a non-electrolyte (Δ 9.76 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$) and is analogous to complex of BDPO with iron(III) chloride.

The phosphoryl stretching frequencies in MDPO and EDPO appear as doublets at 1205, 1192 and 1190, 1180 cm^{-1} , respectively while in BDPO and HDPO as singlets at 1182, 1185 cm^{-1} , respectively (Table 1). The $\nu(\text{PO})$ bands appear in the range 1172-1128 cm^{-1} in the complexes either as a singlet or a doublet. There is negative spectral shift of *ca* 22-52 cm^{-1} in $\nu(\text{P}=\text{O})$ indicating that metal-ligand interaction takes place through phosphoryl group. The reflectance spectra is characteristic of iron(III) complexes⁴⁻⁵ and λ_{max} falls in the range 330-645 nm (Table 1). Detailed studies on these as well as a number of related complexes are in progress.

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-Sulphaphenazole Complexes with La^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+}

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In the present investigation, potentiometric studies have been carried out on 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphaphenazole and its complexes with some trivalent metal ions. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphaphenazole was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine in alcohol-DMF mixture for about 2 hr. The crude product was repeatedly crystallised to obtain an analytically pure compound with m. p. 226°.

All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal salts and perchloric acid of A.R. Grade. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations².

Other experimental details were the same as in our earlier communication³.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned that the ligand does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the course of titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after 2 hr. This was further confirmed by taking tlc of a sample titration mixture from time to time.

In the ligand, it is the phenolic-OH group which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the formation curve (B vs $\bar{n}_A$) was plotted. The pK_1^H corresponding to phenolic H was obtained by half integral method at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$. This was further corroborated by plotting the graph of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphaphenazole.

From the titration curves, $\bar{n}$ and pL values for metal-ligand systems were also determined. From the curves ($\bar{n}$ vs pL) $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were determined by half integral method. In the cases of La^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Gd^{3+} complexes, the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was found to be less than 1.78 log units; these were computed by least square method and are reported in Table 1.

TABLE-1

Cations	$t=25^\circ$						
	H^+	La^{3+}	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}	Y^{3+}
$\log K_1$	7.88	7.45	7.4	6.87	6.64	5.08	4.91
$\log K_2$	-	4.52	-	4.80	4.61	-	4.61

The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be $La^{3+} > Pr^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Dy^{3+} > Y^{3+}$.

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A Potentiometric Study on the Complexes of Gadolinium, Erbium and Ytterbium in Aqueous Solution

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THE stability of complex ion or a molecule in a solution is determined by the nature of the central atom and the addends. The most important characteristics of the central atom determining the stability of the complex compounds are the degree of oxidation (the charge of the central ion in case of ionic complexes), the dimensions (ionic radii) and the electronic configuration. From this point of view rare earth metal ions form an interesting group which consist of similar electronic configuration and the trivalent oxidation state. Thus, in the present study the effect of ionic radii and various ligands containing oxygen and nitrogen as donor atoms have been carried out. In previous publications some lower group of rare earth series have been studied¹⁻⁵. In the present paper the rare earths under study are trivalent gadolinium, erbium and ytterbium using the following organic ligands:

- 7-Iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (IOSA)
- 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (OSA)
- 1,2-Dihydroxybenzene (pyrocatechol, PYC)
- 2,3-Dihydroxynaphthalene-6-sulphonic acid (DHNSA)
- 1,2-Dihydroxybenzene-3,5-disulphonic acid (Trivial name Tiron)

Experimental

Chemicals: All the chemicals used were of AnalaR Grade. Stock solutions (0.01 M) of IOSA, OSA, PYC (E. Merck); DHNSA, Tiron (Fluka, A.G.) were freshly prepared in double distilled carbon dioxide free water. The rare earth solutions were prepared by dissolving rare earth metal trioxide (Johnson and Matthey) in minimum quantity of perchloric acid and standardized by complexometric method⁶.

Instruments: A pH meter (Toshniwal CAT No. CL-43 Type) with combined glass-calomel electrode assembly was used to obtain pH of solutions during the titration. Nitrogen gas was passed continuously during the course of titration. The titration cell was immersed in an electronically controlled thermostatic bath maintained at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The contents of the cell were continuously stirred during the titration. The pH meter was calibrated against standard buffers.